

READING AS AN INTERACTIVE PROCESS

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Annotation: The research paper explores that how the students can develop their reading skills by using effective reading approaches. It is acknowledged that the reading comprehension is one of the most important parts in the English curriculum in all education level of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Reading, English Reading Approaches, develop, predicting, proficiency.

INTRODUCTION

It is justified that reading is considered as the ultimate skill to be used in collaboration at school and all over life. In order to look for information obtain knowledge, to read books English is mandatory and often used as the medium of instruction in higher education. According to Anderson, Hiebert, Scott, & Wilkinson 1985, reading is a vital life skill, which ensures a child's success in school and even throughout his life. Children need to learn different reading strategies in primary sections. If a child is not habituated and acquire the reading skill his personal achievement and job success certainly will be lost. Thus, reading is being given importance in the realm of education sector. It is also considered as one of the most challenging areas, which requires more attention in any education institution. Analytical and critical reading is imperative if they want the possible outcome from the materials they are assigned for. The basic idea of this is to understand the purpose

and the author's intention, when reading something. In fact, reading consists of two layers of reality: one that we can see and one that we cannot see¹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is not an easy task to become a good reader. For this, first of all, learners need to set a goal for their reading. Good readers always have a purpose for reading. One of the basic approaches for developing comprehension skill is predicting, which assists the readers set a purpose for their reading. It is evident that good readers utilize their experiences and knowledge to make predictions and formulate ideas as they read. This approach also includes student interaction that creates a sense of interest among the students and improves their understanding of the text. A comparison between the outcome of the actual text and the prediction process will guide the learner to develop his understanding of the text. Some of the approaches for teaching prediction are modeling, predicting throughout the text, with associates, with a graphic planner, or using post-it notes all through the content. Moreover, using title, table of contents, pictures, and key words are also the integral parts of the prediction approach. Another key prediction approach is to give the students task of predicting at specific points through the text, assess the prediction, and review predictions if necessary².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Visualizing

Good readers can also employ their visualization when comprehending a text. Visualization is the process of constructing an image of what is read. This image is stored in the reader's memory as a representation of the reader's interpretation of the text. Teacher's role is an important factor to develop student's writing skill after visualizes setting like-Student can draw or write what comes to

¹ Block, C., & Israel, S. (2015). Reading first and beyond: The complete guide for teachers and literacy coaches. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.

² Corey, S. M. (2013). Action research to improve school practices. New York, NY: Teachers College Press.

their mind after visualizing the content.

Making Connections

In the reading process making connections is one of the important approaches. It is the process of activating the prior knowledge and making a connection with the ideas of the text to their own experiences. If the readers connect their ideas, experiences, beliefs, and the things going on outer world, reading becomes more effective and meaningful. “Text-to-Text, Text-to-Self, Text-to-Worlds” are the approaches which actually help students to build connection. Students can construct connections through text-to-self, photograph, making a chart, or writing. Teachers may ask the students regarding their any kind of experience, which is being given in the events of the text. Drawing, making a chart, writing, and graphic organizations are the common processes of text-to-text connections. Moreover, these text-to-text connections could be based upon how characters in the story relate to each other, or how story elements relate between stories. Students can do text-to-world connections through comparing characters in a story to characters today or comparing the content of the text to the world today. Teachers should provide the students a purpose from asking them to find connections which would help them comprehend the ideas better in the text.

Summarizing

In plain English, summarization is the process of taking a lot of information and creating a condensed version that covers the main points. It requires the reader to determine what is important when reading and to condense the information in the reader’s own words. During the summarizing procedure, the students will be able to differentiate the core ideas from the underneath thoughts. Moreover, through summarizing, students would be able to differentiate the associated knowledge from the unrelated one. Summarizing would enable the readers improving comprehension skill, organizing ideas, and long reading passages which

are usually perceived as threat for the students³.

Questioning

Questioning is another approach which also helps the readers to enhance their own comprehension abilities. Readers can use the questioning before, during, and after English language reading. The questioning process involves readers to ask questions of themselves to construct meaning, improve understanding, find answers, resolve problems, and discover new information. In this approach, the students are expected to come again to the text throughout the reading process to find the answers to the questions asked by the teacher before, during and after English language reading.

CONCLUSION

The results of the reading awareness scale and my personal experience showed that at the beginning of the study, there was a lack of knowledge in the area of reading approach in my students. However, after a comprehensive study, there was an improvement in their success. As a researcher, at the beginning of the study, I had the worries of implementing the English reading approach in the classroom. Moreover, a number of approaches were another hindrance as the students might have found them confusing. Another question was about the success of the students“ using the comprehension approach independently since many of the students were not familiar with these reading comprehension approaches. In order to overcome these obstacles, I had to guide and monitor the students in every step of the process especially for the questioning, inferring, and summarizing approaches. After an intensive study, I have found an unprecedented improvement in my students“ reading comprehension. The journey of this research was rewarding for both my students and me. After this research journey, I have observed the students“ better understanding of the approaches and their comprehension in reading has been improved. This action research was a productive experience. Thus, I have observed

³ Duke, N. K. & Pearson, P. (2015). Effective practices for developing reading comprehension.

an extensive understanding of reading comprehension approaches as well as an improvement in English reading comprehension of my students.

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